

CORRELATION BETWEEN BODY MASS INDEX AND VITAL SIGNS

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Abstract

Objective: The study aims to estimate the correlation between BMI and vital signs (systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, heart rate (pulse), respiratory rate, temperature) in adolescents to ascertain if changes in BMI cause variations in vital signs.

Design: A cross-sectional study was conducted in 300 male adolescents of Govt. High School Kahna. The sample size was calculated using Epi-Info sample size calculator. The subjects were submitted to a standardized method of measurement of weight, height and vital signs. The data was analyzed in IBM SPSS v21.

Results: The results showed that 16 subjects were identified as pre-obese and 141 were labeled as underweight whereas 69 students came out as pre-hypertensive. A significant bivariate Pearson correlation was found ($P < 0.05$) between BMI and systolic blood pressure readings, but the correlation between BMI and the other vital signs i.e. diastolic blood pressure, heart rate (pulse), respiratory rate and temperature was insignificant.

Conclusions: There is a significant positive Pearson correlation between BMI and systolic blood pressure (Pearson correlation = +0.113, p-value = 0.04908). There is however, no significant correlation between BMI and the other 4 vital signs i.e. diastolic blood pressure, heart rate (pulse), respiratory rate and temperature. This signifies that childhood obesity is correlated to increased blood pressure and may predispose to hypertension in the future.

Keywords: Obesity, BMI, Hypertension, Vitals, Overweight, Blood Pressure

Adolescence is characterized by rapid body growth, with changes in amount of body fat. Childhood and adolescent obesity have been identified as risk factors for obesity in adulthood causing various harmful effects on health later, resulting in an increase in morbidity and mortality.

Obesity is characterized by high deposition of fat in the body due to increased intake of calories or decreased physical activity.^{2,3} The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies overweight and obesity on the basis of body mass index (BMI).^{2,3} In 2008, almost 1.46 billion adults of world are overweight and 502 million were obese, whereas 170 million of the children around the world were obese and overweight.^{2,4,5} An epidemic of obesity is being experienced by most of the developing and devel-

oped countries of the world with some variation found within and between the countries.⁶ The increasing industrialization and urbanization in most of the countries has led to changes in diet and behavior in all age groups. The diets are becoming richer in high fat and high-energy nutrients but poorer in micronutrients. In addition, sedentary lifestyles are becoming more prevalent. In many developing countries, chronic under nutrition may co-exist with chronic obesity within the same population.⁷ Obese people have been found to have a significantly higher blood pressure than those who are of normal weight or are lean.⁸ Obesity represents an important risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. Childhood obesity is often associated with the development of hypertension in the future.⁹ The risk factors for cardiovascular

diseases emerge in adolescence and early adulthood¹⁰ and also associated with adiposity in children, reported by many studies.¹¹ Childhood obesity increases the risk of obesity in adulthood and is associated with cardiovascular diseases, lipid disorders and diabetes mellitus.¹² Obesity also causes an increase in respiratory rate and other vital signs.¹³⁻¹⁵

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study was to find out the prevalence of both high or low BMI, and its correlation with vital signs variability of adolescents in Government Boys High School Kahna, Lahore.

METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional study was conducted and convenience sampling technique was used. Written consent was taken from the School Principal. Verbal informed consent was taken from the participants of this study.

The population of the school as determined from the School Principal was 2000 students. The Open Epi Sample Size Calculator was used. The calculated sample size was 285 with a 95% confidence level.

Three hundred male students between the ages 13-18 years were recruited from Government High School Kahna, Lahore for one-year period between December 2016 to December 2017. Female students or those above 18 years or below 13 years were not included in this study.

A Pro forma was designed to collect the information from each student about his or her name, age, weight, height, blood pressure, heart rate (pulse), respiratory rate and temperature.

The name and age were asked from each student. A weight scale was used to measure the weight in kilograms (kg) and measuring tape to measure the height in centimeters (cm) and blood pressures were recorded in mm of Hg with the help of a Stethoscope and Sphygmomanometer. The right radial pulse was palpated to measure the heart rate by

using a wristwatch. The abdominal movements were observed to measure the respiratory rate.

The BMI cutoffs for severely underweight/ moderately underweight/ mildly underweight was <16.0, <17.0 and <18.5 kg/m² respectively. The

	Frequency	Percent
Hypotension	2	0.7
Normal	229	76.3
Pre-Hypertensive	69	23.0
Total	300	100.0

BMI cutoffs for pre-obese/obese as per the WHO classifications were 25, and 30 kg/m², respectively.¹⁶

The Systolic Blood Pressure cutoffs for hypotension was <90 mmHg. The Systolic Blood Pressure cutoffs for pre-hypertension/ stage 1 hypertension/ stage 2 hypertension were >120, >140 and >160 mmHg.¹⁷

The Diastolic Blood Pressure cutoffs for hypotension was <60 mmHg. The Diastolic Blood Pressure cutoffs for pre-hypertension/ stage 1 hypertension/ stage 2 hypertension were >80, >90 and >100 mmHg.¹⁷

The Heart Rate (Pulse) cutoffs for bradycardia and tachycardia were <60 bpm and >100 bpm respectively.¹⁸

The Respiratory Rate cutoffs for Brachypnea (Hypoventilation) and Tachypnea (Hyperventilation) were <12 and >20 breaths per minute respectively.¹⁸ While the Temperature cutoffs for Hypothermia and Hyperthermia were <95°F and >99.5°F respectively.

The data was collected by measuring the above stated parameters for 5 hours daily for three consecutive days on a pre-printed Pro forma provided by IFMSA and was entered and analyzed in IBM SPSS Statistics Ver.21.

RESULTS

BMI

The results showed that out of 300 subjects, 32

	Frequency	Percent
Severe Underweight	32	10.7
Moderately Underweight	37	12.3
Mildly Underweight	72	24.0
Normal	138	46
Pre-Obese	21	7.0
Total	300	100.0

(10.7%) were severely underweight whereas 37 (12.3%) were moderately underweight and 72 (24.0%) were mildly underweight. 138 subjects (46%) were of normal weight and 21 subjects (7%) were pre-obese.

SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE

2 subjects (0.6%) were hypotensive. 229 subjects (76.3%) presented with normal systolic blood pressure and 69 subjects (23%) were pre-hypertensive.

From 32 subjects that fall under severe underweight category, 30 were with normal blood pressure whereas one was pre-hypertensive and one was

		BMI-Systolic Blood Pressure Crosstab			
		Hypotension	Normal	Pre-Hypertensive	Total
BMI	Severe Underweight	1	30	1	32
	Moderately Underweight	1	33	3	37
	Mildly Underweight	0	53	19	72
	Normal	0	104	34	138
	Pre-Obese	0	9	12	21
Total		2	229	69	300

hypotensive. From 37 subjects that fall under moderately underweight category 33 were with normal blood pressure. 3 students were pre-hypertensive and 1 student was hypotensive. Out of 72 subjects that fall under mildly underweight category, 53 subjects were with normal blood pressure and 19 were pre-hypertensive. Regarding the weight parameters, 138 subjects that fall under normal weight category. 104 were with normal blood pressure whereas 34 subjects were pre-hypertensive. From 21 subjects that fall under pre-obese category, 9 subjects were with normal blood pressure. 12 subjects were pre-hypertensive.

There was a significant correlation between categorical data of BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure (Pearson Correlation Coefficient= 0.113, $p < 0.05$).

DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE

Measuring the diastolic blood pressure, 1 subject (0.3%) was hypotensive while 253 subjects

	Frequency	Percent
Hypotensive	1	0.3
Normal	253	84.3
Pre-Hypertensive	16	5.3
Stage 1 Hypertensive	25	8.3
Stage 2 Hypertensive	5	1.7
Total	300	100.0

(84.3%) were with normal diastolic blood pressure. 16 subjects (5.3%) were pre-hypertensive while 25 subjects (8.3%) were stage 1 hypertensive and 5 subjects (1.7%) were Stage 2 hypertensive.

From 32 subjects that fall under severe underweight category, 29 were with normal blood pressure. 2 were pre-hypertensive. 1 was stage 1 hypertensive. From 37 subjects that fall moderately underweight category, 30 were with normal blood pressure whereas 5 were pre-hypertensive and 2 were stage 1 hypertensive. From 72 subjects that fall under mildly underweight category 61 subjects were with normal blood pressure. 6 were pre-hypertensive while 4 were stage 1 hypertensive and 1 was stage 2 hypertensive. From 138 subjects that fall under normal weight

category 1 subject was hypotensive. 116 were with normal blood pressure. 2 subjects were pre-hypertensive. 15 were stage 1 hypertensive. 4 were stage 2 hypertensive. From 21 subjects that fall under pre-obese category 17 subjects were with normal blood pressure. 1 subject was pre-hypertensive. 3 subjects were stage 1 hypertensive. There was an insignificant correlation between the categorical data of BMI and Diastolic Blood Pressure (Pearson Correlation Coefficient=0.067, p>0.05).

HEART RATE

1 subject (0.3%) had bradycardia. 293 subjects (97.7) had normal pulse rate. 6 subjects (2 %) had

weight category all 32 subjects had normal pulse rate. From 37 subjects that fall under moderately underweight category all 37 subjects had normal pulse rate. From 72 subjects that fall under mildly underweight category 1 subject had bradycardia. 65 subjects were with normal pulse rate. 6 subjects had tachycardia. From 138 subjects that fall under normal weight category all 138 subjects had normal pulse rate. From 21 subjects that fall under pre-obese category all 21 subjects had normal pulse rate.

There was an insignificant correlation between the categorical data of BMI and Heart rate (Pearson Correlation Coefficient=-0.108, p>0.05).

	Frequency	Percent
Bradycardia	1	0.3
Normal	293	97.7
Tachycardia	6	2.0
Total	300	100.0

tachycardia.

From 32 subjects that fall under severe under-

		BMI-Systolic Blood Pressure Crosstab			
		Bradycardia	Normal	Tachycardia	Total
BMI	Severe Underweight	0	32	0	32
	Moderately Underweight	0	37	0	37
	Mildly Underweight	1	65	6	72
	Normal	0	138	0	138
	Pre-Obese	0	21	0	21
Total		1	293	6	300

RESPIRATORY RATE

3 subjects (1%) were suffering from hypo-

ventilation. 238 subjects (79.3%) had a normal respiratory rate. 59 subjects (19.7%) were suffering

	Frequency	Percent
Hypoventilation	3	1.0
Normal	238	79.3
Hyperventilation	59	19.7
Total	300	100.0

from hyperventilation.

		BMI-Respiratory Rate Blood Pressure Crosstab			
		Hypoventilation	Normal	Hyperventilation	Total
BMI	Severe Underweight	0	25	7	32
	Moderately Underweight	2	32	3	37
	Mildly Underweight	0	57	15	72
	Normal	1	104	33	138
	Pre-Obese	0	20	1	21
Total		3	238	59	300

From 32 subjects that fall under severe underweight category all 25 subjects had normal respiratory rate. 7 subjects had hyperventilation. From 37 subjects that fall under moderately underweight category 2 subjects had hypoventilation. 32 subjects had normal respiratory rate. 3 subjects had hyperventilation. From 72 subjects that fall under mildly underweight category 57 subjects were with normal respiratory rate. 15 subjects had hyperventilation. From 138 subjects that fall under normal weight category 1 subject had hypoventilation. 104 subjects had normal respiratory rate. 33 subjects had hyperventilation. From 21 subjects that fall under pre-obese category 20 subjects had normal respiratory rate. 1 subject had hyperventilation.

There was an insignificant correlation between the categorical data of BMI and Respiratory Rate (Pearson Correlation Coefficient= -0.026, p>0.05).

TEMPERATURE

	Frequency	Percent
Hypothermia	3	1.0
Normal	284	94.7
Hyperthermia	13	4.3
Total	300	100.0

3 subjects (1%) were hypothermic. 284 subjects (94.7%) had a normal body temperature. 13 subjects (4.3%) were hyperthermic.

		BMI-Temperature Crosstab			
		Hypothermia	Normal	Hyperthermia	Total
BMI	Severe Underweight	0	31	1	32
	Moderately Underweight	2	34	1	37
	Mildly Underweight	0	67	5	72
	Normal	1	131	6	138
	Pre-Obese	0	21	0	21
Total		3	284	13	300

From thirty two subjects that fall under severe underweight category 31 subjects had normal body temperature. 1 subject was hyperthermic. From 37 subjects that fall under moderately underweight category 2 subjects were hypothermic. 34 subjects had normal body temperature. 1 subject was hyperthermic. From 72 subjects that fall under mildly underweight category 67 subjects had normal body temperature. 5 subjects were hyperthermic. From 138 subjects that fall under normal weight category 1

subject was hypothermic 131 subjects had normal body temperature. 6 subjects were hyperthermic. From 21 subjects that fall under pre-obese category all 21 subjects had normal body temperature.

There was an insignificant correlation between the categorical data of BMI and Temperature (Pearson Correlation Coefficient = -0.073, $p > 0.05$).

Significance Tests (P-value)

	BMI	
	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	P-Value
Systolic Blood Pressure	.113	.049
Diastolic Blood Pressure	.067	.247
Heart Rate (Pulse)	-.108	.061
Respiratory Rate	-.026	.656
Temperature	-.073	.209

The bivariate Pearson correlation test was used to assess the significance of correlation between BMI and Vital Signs. A p-value less than 0.05 denotes significance between two variables.

The results show that there is a significant positive correlation between BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure (Pearson correlation = +0.113, p-value = 0.0498). There is however, no significant correlation between BMI and the other 4 vital signs i.e. Diastolic Blood Pressure, Pulse, Respiratory Rate and Temperature.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates the correlation of Body Mass Index with the Vital Signs i.e. Systolic Blood Pressure, Diastolic Blood Pressure, Heart Rate, Respiratory Rate and Temperature. The hypothesis was to demonstrate raised vital signs on high BMI. The null hypothesis says that there is no significant correlation between BMI and Vital Signs. This study shows a significant Pearson correlation between BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure ($p < 0.05$), so the null hypothesis is rejected. Nevertheless, the correlation between BMI and Heart Rate, Pulse and Temperature is insignificant ($p > 0.05$), so the null hypothesis is accepted for these three variables.

Many previous studies^{(8)(9)(10)(11)(19)(20)(21, 22)(23)} have

shown that obese children had significantly higher Blood Pressure than nonobese children. The similarity between the results of this study and above documented studies signifies that there must be a positive correlation between BMI and Blood Pressure.

There is an incidental finding in this study that signifies another major issue in our society. This study was conducted in a school for lower or lower-middle class children where, out of 300 subjects, 141 (47%) were underweight. 138 (46%) children were of normal weight and 21 children (7%) were pre-obese. This shows that there is a very high ratio (47%) of underweight children among the selected population of lower-middle class children compared to the global average prevalence of 13.5% underweight children according to UNICEF, WHO⁽²⁴⁾. This finding points to the fact that more poverty leads to greater prevalence of low weight among children. A study⁽²³⁾ in Hong Kong, China shows that lower family socioeconomic status is associated with higher risk of obesity and hypertension in childhood, whereas lower neighborhood socioeconomic status is associated with higher risk in underweight, overweight, and obesity.

The increasing prevalence worldwide has led to more attention being given to obesity in childhood and its long-term effects in adults. Many studies have been performed to assess the short- and long-term effects of childhood obesity on health. As our study proves a significant relationship between BMI and Systolic and Diastolic Blood Pressure, so, in application of this research, we can spread awareness among the population about the effects of overweight on blood pressure, so as to guide them about the risks of developing hypertension in the future.

This study may be compared to other similar studies and can further improve by continuing as a prospective cohort study on the same patients. The study results can be compared between students of government and private schools or between males and females. Different other techniques to assess child malnutrition e.g. Triceps skin fold thickness, blood sugar levels, blood vitamin levels etc. can also be used to analyze the various aspects of malnutrition in the community.

CONCLUSION

There is a significant positive Pearson correlation between BMI and systolic blood pressure (Pearson correlation= +0.113, p-value= 0.04908). There is however, no significant correlation between BMI and the other 4 vital signs i.e. diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate and temperature. This signifies that since childhood obesity is correlated to increased blood pressure, it may predispose to hypertension in the future.

The government should take appropriate steps to guide and aware the population about good dietary habits and an active lifestyle, so as to minimize the prevalence of overweight and underweight and to control the incidence and prevalence of hypertension.

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